

Environmental Scan Summary

The following provides an overview of neighbourhood assets and potential barriers/gaps for older adults. The features were identified through a structured assessment in mid-late 2019. As such, this summary should be viewed as an overview of key features observed rather than an exhaustive list.

Stinson and Corktown appeared to be mature neighborhoods. The trees were large and there were several older looking apartments. The sidewalks in Corktown were accessible; however, in Stinson, many roads on the southern side were lacking sidewalks. This could pose a challenge for pedestrians. Garbage and recycling were managed well and lots of greenery was evident in Corktown. In Stinson, garbage and recycling (such as socks, gloves and broken bottles) were noticed on the sidewalks. More young people were seen outside than older people and a few homeless people were observed. The people were mostly Caucasian with minimal cultural diversity. Christian churches were the most common place of worship.

Services appeared to be scattered throughout the two neighbourhoods, more so towards the busier streets, James Street South and Main Street South. The main recreation facility was the Central Memorial Recreation Centre. This centre provides swimming lessons and aqua fitness programs for older adults. There were convenient drop-in schedules, which allows participants flexibility. A YMCA was also noted which has programs geared towards older adults. This neighbourhood also has housing geared towards older adults such as Baywood Place, Stinson Manor, and Jerelday Lodge.

No protective services, such as Police or Fire departments, were identified in this neighbourhood. No Frills was the only grocery store noted, however, there was a diverse range of retail stores including convenience stores, gas stations, Canadian Tire, Discount Car Rental, and Dollarama. Several food outlet stores were also observed including but not limited to Tim Hortons, Coco, Indian Cuisine, and Dominos. Many sheltered bus stops and buses were available for transit within Hamilton, along with a GO terminal, including bus and train for transit outside of Hamilton. Again, many health and social services are apparent including in both Stinson and Corktown, accessible to the older adult population.

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Sihota D., Tandon M., Nadarajah A., Wang A., and De Panfilis L. on behalf of the EMBOLDEN research team (2019). Environmental scan: Corktown and Stinson. URL: <https://emboldenstudy.mcmaster.ca/projects-results/>

Map of services identified in Stinson and Corktown

Index of services

Map Number	Description
Education	
1	Academy of Learning - Career College
2	AlphaBee Learning Centre
3	Central Health Institute
4	Columbia International College
5	Queen Victoria Elementary School
6	Stinson School
Fitness/Recreation	
7	Central Memorial Recreation Centre
Food Sources	
8	Denninger's
9	Hasty Market
10	Narula's Express Indian Cuisine
11	No Frills
12	PizzaWorld
13	Tea Hut
14,15	Tim Hortons
Health/Social Services	
16	ACT Methadone Clinic
17	Barrett Centre for Mental Health Crisis Support
18	Canadian Centre for Occupational Health & Safety
19	Canadian Mental Health Association
20	Catholic Family Services of Hamilton
21	Child and Youth Trauma Services
22	Dental Laboratory Services
23	Dr. B Maleki Ophthalmology

24	Dr. Chung Dao GP Dermatologist
25	Dr. Gulati Family Dentistry
26	Dr. Michele Pakozdi Endodontist
27	EJC Dentistry
28	Excel Dental
29	Gibsons N L Drugs
30	Hamilton Centre for Newcomer Health
31	Hamilton Downtown Family YMCA*
32	Hearing Life
33	Hera Rejuvenation Clinic for Women
34	HRC Counselling Group
35	Immigrants Working Centre
36	Labourers International Union of North America
37	LifeLabs Medical Laboratory Services
38	Lynn Baxter Psychotherapy
39	Main Health Pharmacy
40	Medical Arts Building
41	Momentum Autism Services
42	Northstar Wellness
43	OATC Hamilton Clinic
44	OMG Periodontal Specialist and Dental Implants
45	Physiotherapy, Chiropractor and Massage
46	Rexall Drugstore
47	Saberton Denture and Implant
48	Smile Design Dental Care
49	The Hamilton Academy of Medicine
50	The Hamilton Clinic

Housing

- 51 [Arcadia Apartments](#)
- 52 [Baywoods Place*](#)
- 53 [Brockton Apartments](#)
- 54 Burbank Place Apartments
- 55 [Charwal Apartments](#)
- 56 [Corktown Co-operative Homes](#)
- 57 [Donna Court Apartments](#)
- 58 [Duchess Apartments](#)
- 59 Emerald Lodge
- 60 [Erie Manor](#)
- 61 [Gumiero Holdings Inc](#)
- 62 Hunters Green Condos
- 63 [James & Forest](#)
- 64 Jerelday Lodge*
- 65 [Marlis Place Apartment](#)
- 66 Medallion Corporation
- 67 Medallion Properties
- 68 [Oakland Square II Apartments](#)
- 69 [Renaissance Towers](#)
- 70 [Residences on Augusta](#)
- 71 Stinson Manor*
- 72 [Stinson Town Apartment](#)
- 73 The Carlisle
- 74 Timbercreek
- 75 [Topaz Apartments](#)
- 76 Villa Marie Apartments
- 77 Wellington St S Apartments
- 78 [Winston Place Apartments](#)

Parks

- 79 [Bishop's Park](#)
- 80 Carter Park
- 81 Corktown Park
- 82 Shamrock Park
- 83 St. Joseph's Park
- 84 [Woolverton Park](#)

Religious Centres

- 85 [Access Community Church of God](#)
- 86 [Church of the Ascension](#)
- 87 [Samudra Kadampa Buddhist Centre](#)
- 88 [St. Charles Garnier Church](#)
- 89 The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints

Retail Stores

- 90 Anytime Convenience
- 91 [Canadian Tire](#)
- 92 [Discount Car Rental](#)
- 93 [Dollarama](#)
- 94 [Dollarama](#)
- 95 [Downtown Auto Specialist](#)
- 96 Elegant Barber Shop
- 97 Pioneer Gas Station
- 98 The Owl of Minerva
- 99 Town Convenience

Transportation

- 100 [Hamilton GO Centre](#)

*Programs Targeted Specifically at older adults

Environmental Scan Update, 2022

The neighbourhood's programs and services appeared relatively consistent with those available for the community in the initial environmental scan completed in 2019. The initial environmental scan identified 60 relevant services across various categories; presently, 66 services have been identified though the distribution of services has varied across the two time points. Minor changes are seen in the number of services across categories in fitness/recreation, health/social services, housing, and protective services (Table 1). These changes can be attributed to services no longer being operational due to COVID-19-related closures and other operational status changes e.g., changes in management, location changes, construction, etc. For example, Central Memorial Recreation Centre has been temporarily closed for maintenance with a predicted reopening date in Fall 2022. Additionally, healthcare practices such as Dr. B Maleki Ophthalmology, which provides surgical procedures to enhance eye health, have been permanently relocated to Toronto. Likewise, Lynn Baxter Psychotherapy, which provides mental health services, has also been permanently relocated to St. Catherine's.

In terms of newly identified services, Globe FC, a local soccer club for children and young adults, and Keddy Access Trail, a local trail path in the neighbourhood, were identified and categorized within fitness/recreation services. Hamilton Community Legal Clinic, Greenbank Concussion Clinic, Go Dental - Dr. Jan Hanna, and Hamilton Mental Health Outreach were all services newly identified within the health/social services category. They support various social and health needs in the community. For example, Hamilton Community Legal Clinic provides legal services to low-income individuals and the Greenbank Concussion Clinic provides concussion health services as well as educational materials on the topic. Go Dental - Dr. Jan Hanna provides dental services in the neighbourhood and Hamilton Mental Health Outreach supports individuals with mental illness and addiction. Many organizations did not provide

services and programs that were exclusively for the older adult age group. However, the services were open to all age groups.

Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic had varying degrees of impact on service delivery within the community, with most identified services remaining opening to serve the community in person. Table 2 provides a detailed list of services within the Corktown & Stinson neighbourhood and their current operational status (as impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic).

Table 1. Summary of number of services and their current operational status

	Number of Services (2019)	Number of Services (2022)	Open, in-person	Open with online options available	Unclear status	Closed
Education	2	2	2			
Fitness/ Recreation	1	2	2			1
Food Sources	6	6	6			
Health/Social Services	19	21	19	2		2
Housing	13	14	13		1	
Parks	4	4	4			
Protective Services	5	6	5		1	
Religious Centres	3	3	2	1		
Stores	7	7	7			
Transportation	1	1	1			
Total	60	66	61	3	2	3

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Table 2. Summary of Services COVID-19 Status and Function

Open, in-person (with modified procedures for public safety)	Open with online options available	Unclear status (with attempt to contact)	Closed
Education			
Columbia International College Queen Victoria Elementary School			
Fitness/Recreation			
Globe FC Keddy Access Trail			Central Memorial Recreation Centre¹
Food Sources			
Denninger's Hasty Market Narula's Express Indian Cuisine Tea Hut Tim Hortons (Jackson St E and John St S) Tim Hortons (St. Joseph's Healthcare Hamilton)			
Health/Social Services			
Canadian Centre for Occupational Health and Safety Canadian Mental Health Association Hamilton Centre for Newcomer Health Hamilton Downtown Family YMCA HearingLife Hera Rejuvenation Clinic for Women Immigrants Working Centre Labourers International Union of North America² LifeLabs Medical Laboratory Services Medical Arts Building Momentum Autism Services Saberton Denture and Implant Smile Design Dental Care			
			Dr. B Maleki Ophthalmology Lynn Baxter Psychotherapy Hamilton Mental Health Outreach

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Open, in-person (with modified procedures for public safety)	Open with online options available	Unclear status (with attempt to contact)	Closed
The Hamilton Academy of Medicine The Hamilton Clinic Hamilton Community Legal Clinic Greenbank Concussion Clinic Go Dental - Dr. Jan Hanna			
Housing			
Arcadia Apartments Brockton Apartments Charwal Apartments Corktown Co-operative Homes James & Forest Medallion Properties Oakland Square II Apartments Renaissance Towers Residences On Augusta Topaz Apartments Villa Marie Apts Winston Place Apartments Mainwell Apartments - Hazelview Properties		Corktown Co-operative Homes	
Parks			
Corktown Park Shamrock Park St. Joseph's Park Woolverton Park			
Protective Services			
Mackesy Smye Personal Injury Law Firm Martin Vamos Family Law Provincial Offences Offices Simpson Wigle LAW LLP M Gibson Legal - Real Estate and Mortgage Law		Amy Katz & Associates Professional Corporation	
Religious Centres			
Church of the Ascension St. Charles Garnier Church	Access Community Church of God		

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Open, in-person (with modified procedures for public safety)	Open with online options available	Unclear status (with attempt to contact)	Closed
Stores			
Anytime Convenience Canadian Tire Discount Car Rental Dollarama Downtown Auto Specialist Pioneer Gas Station Town Convenience/BIG BEE FOODMART			
Transportation			
Hamilton GO Centre			

¹ Central Memorial Recreation Centre is temporarily closed for maintenance beginning August 22, 2022, with a predicted reopening date in late Fall 2022 (date to be determined).

² Labourers International Union of North America is temporarily relocated though still operational and open to the public.

³ ACT Methadone Clinic is open with telemedicine options.

⁴ HRC Counselling Group is open and operational, however it is no longer accepting new patients at this time and all services are virtual.

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Based on 2021 Census Data

CT Highlights

Population
= 5,691

Number of Homes
= 3,481

Population Density
= 6,256/Km²

5-year Population change = 8.2%

Age Distribution by Gender

Income & Employment

Citizenship & Immigrant Population

Canadian Citizens

Immigrants Recent Immigrants

Language Spoken at Home

English | 75.1%
Non-official Languages | 19.6%

Highest Certificate, Diploma or Degree

■ No certificate, diploma or degree
■ Secondary (high) school diploma or equivalency
■ Postsecondary certificate, diploma or degree

Neighbourhood Homes

\$1,535_(own)
\$1,122_(rent)

Average monthly shelter costs

80%

Rent their home

\$452,000

Average home value

70%

Apartment ≥ 5 stories

75%

Built before 1980

14%

Major repair needed

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Infographic: Neighbourhood Profile of Stinson-Corktown. URL:

<https://emboldenstudy.mcmaster.ca/projectresults/>

Data Source: Statistics Canada. 20215370034.00 [Census tract].
www.statcan.gc.ca